

**MODELS AND METHODS FOR
INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF
INNOVATIVE RESEARCH**
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SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL BASES OF DEVELOPMENT OF MARKETING LOGISTICS IN WHOLESALE TRADE

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Abstract: *This article focuses on the fact that marketing logistics is an important means of gaining a competitive advantage in the wholesale business. The role of marketing and logistics in wholesale trade, the content of marketing logistics, the peculiarities of the application of marketing logistics in wholesale trade are described.*

Keywords: *wholesale, marketing concepts, marketing logistics, marketing functions, distribution channels, storage, delivery.*

Introduction

Any business activity is aimed at meeting the needs of customers. In particular, wholesale organizations and enterprises achieve the end result through a high level of customer service, efficient delivery of goods in accordance with consumer requirements. In this case, the cost and resources should be kept to a minimum.

Marketing and logistics functions play an important role in wholesale brand purchasing and sales activities. Marketing and logistics work together to achieve the goals set in the wholesale business. Marketing activities are aimed at identifying consumer demand and offering it the goods it needs. Logistics, on the other hand, involves delivering existing goods on time, in the required quantity and place, and providing a high level of customer service. The evolution of logistics and marketing development has led to the merging of their functions and the consequent emergence of marketing logistics.

The concept of marketing logistics is seen as an effective organization of the flow of goods in the distribution channels and marketing management system in order to achieve sustainable competitive advantages, improve service quality and optimize costs. Implementation of the conceptual rules of marketing logistics provides the solution of the following tasks: formation of value creation system for consumers through coordination of distribution channel participants, formation of value creation system for consumers through coordination, integration of marketing and logistics functions of distribution channel participants, high quality service meet

the needs of consumers, increase the profitability of marketing activities by optimizing the costs in the supply chain.

Hence, the role of wholesale trade in the organization and management of commodity flows in distribution channels is invaluable. In today's fiercely competitive environment, wholesalers are also facing strong competitors. Marketing logistics is an important means of gaining a competitive advantage in wholesale trade.

The main part

As a result of the economic reforms carried out in Uzbekistan in recent years, the rules of a market economy are systematically applied in all sectors and industries of the economy. The changing competitive environment in the commodity and financial markets, the intensity of competition in all sectors is increasing. This process highlights the need to develop sustainable and long-term strategies for businesses to gain a competitive advantage.

Enterprises achieve competitive advantage in practice by maintaining a competitive advantage through the application of marketing concepts that allow them to meet the needs of consumers in a combination of quality and price, and by optimizing the flow of goods and materials from a logistical point of view.

A number of scientific studies confirm that enterprise management, which has proven its effectiveness in a free market environment, has been achieved through the integration of marketing and logistics concepts. An analysis of the available literature has shown that we can now see that there are three main approaches to the interrelationship of marketing and logistics.

According to the first approach, marketing is a set of processes in a company to form demand, move a product, and manage sales. Logistics solves issues related to the process of warehousing, storage, physical distribution of finished products to consumers, supply of raw materials and other material resources to manufacturing enterprises, the management of the movement of inventory. The growing problems of resource supply of production processes, factors related to the optimization of the sales process in the face of growing competition, led to the emergence of the concept of logistics in the 60s.

Today, logistics includes the management of trade operations, analysis of supplier and consumer markets, coordination of supply and demand in the market of goods and services. It is clear that logistics issues are intertwined with marketing issues.

Most of the authors consider marketing and logistics as independent production and economic activities that are closely related to each other.

Using marketing tools, the company identifies its customers, what products they need, how much they need. Logistics tools ensure the optimal organization of the flow of goods and materials in the enterprise, the timely delivery of finished products to consumers, in the required volume, in the right place. It can be seen that both of these tools in enterprise operations solve different functional tasks and in no case are they interchangeable. Only their joint use can guarantee the efficiency of the enterprise. Businesses can use both marketing and logistics independently in their activities.

Thus, using only the marketing concept, an enterprise cannot effectively move its products in the market. This is because unresolved logistics issues of delivery, transportation and storage of goods can hinder this. In modern conditions of market saturation, when the traditional motivational criteria of the consumer (quality and price of goods) are left behind, these issues are almost solved when the consumer decides to buy.

Marketing and logistics are inseparable. Because together they form the general conditions and policy of production, supply and sales activities of the enterprise. The skillful use of both tools at the same time, in harmony, gives a much greater synergistic effect than using each one separately.

Conclusion

Today, the idea of combining marketing and logistics functions in wholesale trade is being promoted. This process is based on marketing logistics. Marketing logistics is an activity related to the production of raw materials, spare parts, materials, components from the point of origin, planning the distribution channels of finished products, the delivery of finished products based on the study of consumer needs.

Marketing logistics in wholesale trade is aimed at forming an order portfolio, planning production assortment based on it, determining the optimal product movement technology, setting standards for product quality and packaging, eliminating delivery time losses, efficient use of material and labor resources.

Modern information technologies play an important role in wholesale marketing logistics. Digital technologies, wholesale terminals, uniform coding of goods, satellite tracking of goods, computerization of warehouse operations, electronic data exchange and remittances are carried out through marketing logistics in wholesale trade.

The task of marketing logistics in wholesale trade is to manage the supply of the manufacturer, the flow of finished products from producer to consumer. In wholesale sales, marketing logistics is the analysis, planning, organization and

management of all operations related to product storage, delivery, movement route, communication, order portfolio formation, service.

Marketing logistics is critical to increasing the efficiency of brand movement in wholesale and reducing costs. Marketing logistics is the design and implementation of infrastructure in wholesale trade, which involves the efficient and cost-effective delivery of goods from the source of origin to the point of sale.

The main purpose of marketing logistics in wholesale trade is to meet the needs and requirements of consumers in a timely manner with quality goods and services and services, to establish strong, long-term relationships and relationships with customers, delivery to the right place at the right time.

The main activity of marketing logistics in wholesale trade is related to running a business. This is an important component of the marketing and logistics system of wholesale businesses. The genesis of marketing and logistics functions in wholesale trade often depends on the nature of the industry. Here we are talking about the functions of marketing and logistics services in the implementation of commercial activities of market participants.

It should be noted that marketing logistics in wholesale trade activities is aimed at:

- reduction of inventories and associated capital;
 - increase readiness for delivery of goods;
 - reduce order fulfillment time and improve its quality;
 - increasing the flexibility of production;
 - reduction of production costs, transportation costs, manual labor costs;
 - acceleration of capital turnover;
 - optimization of economic flows of the enterprise;
 - optimization of the organization of use of all types of enterprise resources;
- Coordinating the activities of all divisions of the enterprise in the process of managing economic flows.

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